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New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Stable-Cut pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

E' is Stable;

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

E' is Stable;

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

V' is Stable;

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

V' is Stable;

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic

v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; a Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the

Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperStable-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegance and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The “Cancer’s Recognition” are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called “SuperHyperVertex” but the relations amid them all officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. The frameworks “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” are chosen and elected to research about “Cancer’s Recognition”. Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and “Cancer’s Recognition”. Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It’s also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut is a maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It’s useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. Since there’s more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperStable-Cut more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there’s a need to “redefine” the notion of a “SuperHyperStable-Cut”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there’s the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Cut. It’s redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, “The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with the key points, “The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet”, “The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints”. To get structural examples and instances, I’m

going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperStable-Cut . It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperStable-Cut until the SuperHyperStable-Cut, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperStable-Cut" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperStable-Cut . There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperStable-Cut" . These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperStable-Cut . For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" . The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperStable-Cut are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperStable-Cut amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperStable-Cut .] SuperHyperStable-Cut . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is

identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperStable-Cut or the strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperStable-Cut, called SuperHyperStable-Cut, and the strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStable-Cut, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for

this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances’ styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperStable-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperStable-Cut or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “ amount of SuperHyperStable-Cut” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperStable-Cut” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It’s motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “ SuperHyperStable-Cut” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperStable-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, are figured out in sections “

SuperHyperStable-Cut” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Stable-Cut to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “ SuperHyperStable-Cut”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “ SuperHyperStable-Cut”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [120]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [120]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Stable-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a

falsity-membership function of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$. 338
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Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref.** [120], Definition 2.2, p.2). 340

Let X be a Stable-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [120], Definition 2.5, p.2). 341
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Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 343
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 345
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 346
347
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 348
349
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 350
351
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 352
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 353
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 354
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 355
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$. 356

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $T''_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'''_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

and $F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;

- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 464
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that 465
 $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 466

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 467

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 468

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 469
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 470
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 471
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 472
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 474

(Ref. [120], Definition 5.3, p.7). 475

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have 476

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 477
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 478
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 479
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 480

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.4, p.7). 481
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 483
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- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 485
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- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 488
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- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 491
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- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

E' is Stable;

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

E' is Stable;

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

V' is Stable;

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

V' is Stable;

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum

- Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; 531-534
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 535-544
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 545-555
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; 556-563
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; 564-571
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 572-580

Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

- (i) an δ -**SuperHyperStable-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Cut. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the Table (3) holds.

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Definition 4.1. (Neutrosophic event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Any Neutrosophic k -subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Neutrosophic subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic event**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Neutrosophic Independent).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. s Neutrosophic k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Neutrosophic s -independent** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Neutrosophic k -events of A and B is called **Neutrosophic independent**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Neutrosophic Variable).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Any k -function Stable-Cut like E is called **Neutrosophic k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Stable-Cut like E is called **Neutrosophic Variable**.

The notion of independent on Neutrosophic Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Neutrosophic Expectation).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Expectation** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Neutrosophic Crossing).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Neutrosophic number is called **Neutrosophic Crossing** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let m and n propose special Stable-Cut. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Neutrosophic random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Neutrosophic independently with probability Stable-Cut $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Neutrosophic number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Neutrosophic Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

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Theorem 4.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Proof. Form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between consecutive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. □

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Theorem 4.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Neutrosophic number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between consecutive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

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$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. □

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Proposition 4.9. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a nonnegative Neutrosophic Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Stable-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k + 1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Neutrosophic Variable for this Neutrosophic Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p} (k+1)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{ne^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $ne^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Neutrosophic Variance).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Variance** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Variance criteria**

$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then

$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X_n be a Neutrosophic Variable in a probability Stable-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then

$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. $\square$

Theorem 4.15. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. $\square$

Corollary 4.16. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

- (i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* . 770

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. 771
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 772

Definition 4.17. (Neutrosophic Threshold). 773

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 774
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a monotone property of 775
SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a 776
Neutrosophic Threshold for P is a function $f(n)$ such that: 777

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P , 778

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P . 779

Definition 4.18. (Neutrosophic Balanced). 780

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 781
 $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let F be a fixed Neutrosophic 782
SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a 783
copy of F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Neutrosophic Balanced**. 784

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 785
 $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let F be a nonempty 786
balanced Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l 787
SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F 788
as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph. 789

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. 790
Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 791

Example 4.20. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair 792
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 793

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic 794
SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 795
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but 796
 E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic 797
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, 798
there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic 799
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no 800
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the 801
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic 802
SuperHyperStable-Cut. 803

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic 805
SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 806
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges 807

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i \neq 1,5}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 12z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_1, V_6, V_{15}, V_9\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 4 \times 3 \times 4 \times 3z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

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Figure 5. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+2_{i=0^4}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 2 \times 2z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+1_{i=0^4}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 2 \times 2z^{10}.$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} =$$

$$\{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 2z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} =$$

$$\{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 2z^5.$$

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Figure 6. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^4}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^4}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5. \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 9. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 10. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_i\}_{i=4,5,6,9,10}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \\
 &= 2z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} = \\
 & \{E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} = \\
 & \{V_1, V_6\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \\
 &= 3 \times 3z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 13. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_1\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_2, V_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^2}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_{2i+2_{i=0}^1}, V_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 16. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^2}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_1, V_3, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0}^2}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

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Figure 17. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^6. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 18. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 21. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{E_{2i+2_{i=0}^1}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}}$$

$$= \{V_1, H_6, V_7, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= 5 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5z^4.$$

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Figure 22. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Neutrosophic number of type-result-R-Stable-Cut has, the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality, is the Neutrosophic cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \}.$$

If there's a Neutrosophic type-result-R-Stable-Cut with the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for cardinality. 918
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Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally, 920
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

Is a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of 922
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Stable-Cut since neither amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality indicates that these Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Neutrosophic lower bound in the term of Neutrosophic sharpness. In other words, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}.$$

Is a quasi-R-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Stable-Cut. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Neutrosophic structure of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut decorates the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Neutrosophic connections so as this Neutrosophic style implies different versions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Neutrosophic bound is to have the maximum Neutrosophic groups of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have perfect Neutrosophic connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph arising from its Neutrosophic properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, then there's no Neutrosophic connection. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic existence of one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no Neutrosophic effect to talk about the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Since at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Neutrosophic background of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge but at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices make the Neutrosophic version of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Neutrosophic setting of non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Neutrosophic adjective for the initial Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Neutrosophic appearance of the loop Neutrosophic version of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and this Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Neutrosophic adjective "loop" on the basic Neutrosophic framework engages one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Neutrosophic setting. With these Neutrosophic bases, on a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut has the Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut has the Neutrosophic cardinality at least a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut since either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Neutrosophic usage of this Neutrosophic framework and even more there's no Neutrosophic connection inside or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Neutrosophic contradiction with the term "Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut" since the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality never happens for this Neutrosophic style of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Neutrosophic connection inside as mentioned in first Neutrosophic case in the forms of drawback for this selected Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Comes up. This Neutrosophic case implies having the Neutrosophic style of on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style on the every Neutrosophic elements of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that some Neutrosophic amount of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style. The Neutrosophic cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

But the lower Neutrosophic bound is up. Thus the minimum Neutrosophic cardinality of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality ends up the Neutrosophic discussion. The first Neutrosophic term refers to the Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClass of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style amid some amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. This Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel proposes a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has only some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Neutrosophic amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The Neutrosophic cardinality of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Neutrosophic case is occurred in the minimum Neutrosophic situation. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Has the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Contains some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices taken from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

It means that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}$$

Is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as used
Neutrosophic background in the Neutrosophic terms of worst Neutrosophic case and the
common theme of the lower Neutrosophic bound occurred in the specific Neutrosophic
SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are Neutrosophic
free-quasi-triangle.

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic
number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Then every Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertex has at least no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with others in
common. Thus those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be
contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are
potentially included in a Neutrosophic style-R-Stable-Cut. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge
 $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The formal
definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and there's only and
only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut but with
slightly differences in the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality amid those Neutrosophic
type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Neutrosophic cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Let
 $Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut =

$$\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \overset{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}.$$

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Neutrosophic intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Neutrosophic Stable-Cut, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Neutrosophic optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut where the Neutrosophic completion of the Neutrosophic incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Neutrosophic embedded R-Stable-Cut. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality and they're Neutrosophic SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Neutrosophic style of the embedded Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. The interior types of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices pose the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Thus Neutrosophic exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and in Neutrosophic SuperHyperRelation with the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Neutrosophic Stable-Cut, there's the usage of exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the

title “exterior” is more relevant than the title “interior”. One Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. The Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut with the inclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There’s only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there’s only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut has two titles. a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut and its corresponded quasi-maximum Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Neutrosophic number, there’s a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut with that quasi-maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If there’s an embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, then the Neutrosophic quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cuts for all Neutrosophic numbers less than its Neutrosophic corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cuts acted on the all possible used formations of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Neutrosophic number. This Neutrosophic number is considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Stable-Cuts. Let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and a Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal

technical definition for the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. 1015

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut poses the upcoming expressions. 1016

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1018

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} & \\
= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

And then, 1019

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1020

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}] \text{Neutrosophic Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Neutrosophic Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\
= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Cut” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Cut” since “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Cut” happens “Neutrosophic Stable-Cut” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Neutrosophic Stable-Cut” in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Cut”, and “Neutrosophic Stable-Cut” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Neutrosophic Stable-Cut and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid & \\
|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there’s no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge amid some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Neutrosophic Stable-Cut** is related to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There’s not only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Cut is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn’t have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet since they’ve come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Cut**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. There isn't only less than two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Neutrosophic free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Neutrosophic on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Neutrosophic stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut amid those obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. 1062

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. 1063

The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic 1064
quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic 1065
SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually 1066
Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all 1067
Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them. 1068

Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a 1069
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Neutrosophic 1070
SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Neutrosophic numbers of those Neutrosophic 1071
SuperHyperVertices from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge excluding more 1072
than r distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Neutrosophic 1073
SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a 1074
Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic 1075
bound for Neutrosophic cardinality. Assume a connected Neutrosophic 1076
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the 1077
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of 1078
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge 1079
to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Neutrosophic 1080
R-Stable-Cut. Since it doesn't have **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a 1081
Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a 1082
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The 1083
Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is 1084
the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of 1085
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut. Since it 1086
doesn't do the Neutrosophic procedure such that such that there's a Neutrosophic 1087
SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at 1088
least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the 1089
connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Neutrosophic 1090
SuperHyperVertex, titled its Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Neutrosophic 1091
SuperHyperVertex in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the 1092
Neutrosophic procedure"]. There's only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **outside** 1093
the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Neutrosophic 1094
SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut, V_{ESHE} is up. 1095
The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1096
R-Stable-Cut, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** 1097
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Neutrosophic pairs are titled 1098
Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph 1099
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1100
SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the 1101
maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality of a Neutrosophic 1102
SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a 1103
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely. 1104
Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any 1105

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Cut only contains all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from the unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Stable-Cut, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an **Neutrosophic Stable-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Cut is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic

SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut}} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial}} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Neutrosophic Stable-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Cut**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended

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Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Cut,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Cut, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

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“Neutrosophic Stable-Cut”

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amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

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Neutrosophic Stable-Cut,

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is only and only

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

□ 1162

5 The Neutrosophic Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

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The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i+12i+1=||E_{NSHG}||}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{V_{2i+12i+1=||E_{NSHG}||}^{INTERNAL}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= az^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath

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Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.5)

$ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperStable-Cut.

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Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut} &= \{E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= 2z^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut} &= \{V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= az^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut} \\
 &= \{V_i^{INTERNAL}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= az^{\frac{|ESHG|}{2}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.7)

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

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Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

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Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.9)

$ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{ \text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges} \}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^{|\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}|}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2bz^{|\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}|} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\ & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^{|\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}|}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}\} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2bz^{|\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}|} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.11)

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.13)

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

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Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

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$ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= 2z^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1^*, \\ \text{CENTER}, E_2^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\ E_2^*, \text{CENTER} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperStable-Cut proposes some longest SuperHyperStable-Cut excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.12. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, some general results are introduced.

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Neutrosophic Example (16.15)

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets. 1276
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Corollary 6.2. Assume Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then 1278

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable – Cut} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperStable – Cut of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperStable – Cut} \\ & | \text{Neutrosophic cardinality among those SuperHyperStable – Cut.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. 1279
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Corollary 6.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut and SuperHyperStable-Cut coincide. 1282
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Corollary 6.4. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if and only if it’s a SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1285
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Corollary 6.5. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut if and only if it’s a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1288
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Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is its SuperHyperStable-Cut and reversely. 1291
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Corollary 6.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is its SuperHyperStable-Cut and reversely. 1294
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined. 1298
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Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined. 1301
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Corollary 6.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined. 1304
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined. 1308
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Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined. 1311
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Corollary 6.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined. 1314
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then V is 1318
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- (i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1320
- (ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1321
- (iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1322
- (iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1323
- (v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1324
- (vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1325

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1326
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- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1328
- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1329
- (iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1330
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1331
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1332
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1333

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1334
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- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1336

- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1337
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1338
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1339
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1340
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1341

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1342
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- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1345
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1346
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1347
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1348
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1349
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1350

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1351

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1352
1353

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1354
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1355
- (iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1356
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1357
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1358
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1359

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1360

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1361
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- (i) : the SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1364
- (ii) : the SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1365
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1366
- (iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1367
- (v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1368
- (vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1369

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1370
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Proposition 6.20. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of*

- (i) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (ii) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut.

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide.

Proposition 6.21. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a*

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 6.22. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a*

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;
- (vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 6.23. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of*

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;

(ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1410

(iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1411

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1412

(v) : *strong* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1413

(vi) : *connected* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1414

is one and it's only S, a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1415
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Proposition 6.24. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual* 1419
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1421

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1422

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1423

(iv) : *SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1424

(v) : *strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1425

(vi) : *connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1426

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Neutrosophic number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1427
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Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E)) \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1429
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1432

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1433

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1434

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1435

(v) : *strong* $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1436

(vi) : *connected* $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1437

Proposition 6.27. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Neutrosophic number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual* 1438
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1441

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1442

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1443

(iv) : *0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1444

(v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1445

(vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1446

Proposition 6.28. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet. 1447
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Proposition 6.29. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual 1449
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1451
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1453

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1454

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1455

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1456

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1457

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1458

Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \mathcal{O}_{\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual 1459
1460
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1463

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1464

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1465

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1466

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1467

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1468

Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. 1469
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Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that 1474
1475
1476

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1477

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1478

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then 1479
1480

(i) S is SuperHyperStable-Cut set; 1481

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1482

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then 1483
1484

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1485

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1486

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then 1487
1488

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1489

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1490

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then 1491

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1492
1493

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1494

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1495

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1496
1497

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then 1498

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1499

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1500
1501

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1502

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1503
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Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then 1505

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1506
1507

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1508
1509

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1510

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1511
1512

Proposition 6.39. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then 1513

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1514
1515

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1516

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1517

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1518
1519

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1520

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1521

(ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1522

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1523

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1524

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1525

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1526
1527

(ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1528

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)$; 1529

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1530
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Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1532

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1533
1534

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$; 1535

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$; 1536

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1537
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Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1539

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1540
1541

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1542

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1543

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1544
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Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStars with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1546
1547

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1548
1549

(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1550

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1551

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1552
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Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1554
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(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1557
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(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1559

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1560

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1561
1562

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1563
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1565

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1566
1567

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1568

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1569

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1570
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Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1572
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(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1574
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(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1577
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Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1580
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(i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1582
1583
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(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1585
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Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1588
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1591
1592
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1593
1594
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1595
1596
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1597
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Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1599
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- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1602
1603
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1604
1605
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1606
1607
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1608
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Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1610
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1612

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1613
1614
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1615
1616
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1617
1618
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1619
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Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1621
1622
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- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1624
1625
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1626
1627
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1628
1629
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1630
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Proposition 6.53. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperStable-Cut$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$.

Proposition 6.54. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperStable-Cut$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$;
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut$.

7 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

8 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (29), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut

9 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (30), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStable-Cut, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperStable-Cut. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperStable-Cut, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are

formally called “ SuperHyperStable-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperStable-Cut	
3. Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the

- Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1782
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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; 1785
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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1793
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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 1803
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1814
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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; 1822
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(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients
defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its
Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is
a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge.
Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge
has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 ,
is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges
but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that
there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic

SuperHyperDuality.

1870

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1871

1872

1873

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1874

1875

1876

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1877

1878

1879

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1880

1881

1882

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1883

1884

1885

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1886
1887
1888

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1889
1890
1891

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1892
1893
1894

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1895
1896
1897

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1898
1899
1900

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1901
1902
1903

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1904
1905
1906

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1907
1908
1909

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1910
1911
1912

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 1913
1914
1915

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 1916
1917
1918

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 1919
1920
1921

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 1922
1923
1924

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 1925
1926
1927

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 1928
1929
1930

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 1931
1932

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &\underline{E}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, \underline{V}^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then*

1969
1970

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}, \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1971

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

1972
1973

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

1974
1975
1976
1977
1978
1979

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any

1980
1981
1982

solution

1983

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 1984

Example 12.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality. 1985
1986
1987
1988
1989
1990

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 1991
1992

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1993

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1994
1995

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 1996
1997

straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

13 Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2054-2061
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; 2062-2069
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2070-2079
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 2080-2090
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2091-2098
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic 2099-2103

SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin;

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 13.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2147
2148

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2149
2150
2151

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2152
2153
2154

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2155
2156
2157

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2158
2159
2160

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2161
2162
2163

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2164
2165
2166

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2167
2168
2169

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2170
2171
2172

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2173
2174
2175

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2176
2177
2178

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i \neq 5,7,8}^{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2179
2180
2181

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2182
2183
2184

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2185
2186
2187

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2188
2189
2190

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2191
2192
2193

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2194
2195
2196

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2197
2198
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2200
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2203
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2206
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2209
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &\underline{E}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, \underline{V}^{EXTERNAL}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ & = (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

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$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$P :$

$V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$

$V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2,$

$\dots,$

$E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

14 Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

(i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;

(ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;

(iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus

the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2425
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2427
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2430
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2433
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2436
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2439
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2442
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2445
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2448
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2451
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2454
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2457
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2460
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2463
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2466
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2469
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2472
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2475
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=03}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=05}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2478
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2481
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2484
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2487
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Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
 & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
 & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). Then*

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite ESHB : (V, E). There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be

applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the 2534
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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2536
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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 2540

Example 14.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2541
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Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite 2547

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 & = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a

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Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2708
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2711
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2714
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2717
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2720
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly 2723
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2741
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2744
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2747
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2750
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2753
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2756
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2759
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2762
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2765
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Proposition 15.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 2767
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2769

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &\quad \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} V_i^{EXTERNAL} |_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}|$$

$$= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}}$$

$$= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

16 Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected** if 2873
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2874
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ 2875
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected** if 2876
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2877
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ and 2878
 $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2879
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected** if 2880
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such 2881
that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ 2882
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected** if 2883
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a;$ $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that 2884
 $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and 2885
 $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2886
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2887
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2888
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected. 2889

Definition 16.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperConnected). 2890

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 2891
a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 2892

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2893
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2894
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 2895
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 2896
Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 2897
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme 2898
SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 2899
Extreme SuperHyperConnected; 2900
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2901
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2902
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 2903
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 2904
Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic 2905
SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic 2906
SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 2907
Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; 2908
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either 2909
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, 2910
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic 2911
rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph 2912
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme 2913
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality 2914
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high 2915
Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme 2916
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and 2917
the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2918

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

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Example 16.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2995
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2998
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3001
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3004
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3007
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^{19}, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 3010
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3028
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3031
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3034
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3037
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3040
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

Then

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}^z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

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Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i| E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and

SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3175
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The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [76]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3177
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In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022),“(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in 3188
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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [121]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google

Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It's titled "Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs" and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [122]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It's titled "Neutrosophic Duality" and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4-44,46-120]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [121,122].

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